

Role of Substrate Symmetry in Gas-solid Reactions. Part I: Reactions of Gaseous Uranium Oxide with Different Oxides.

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Based on reactions of gaseous UO_3 with different oxides, it is established that the substrate symmetry is important in determining whether chemical reaction takes place or not.

It was shown¹ that U_3O_8 and ThO_2 react in air through the intermediate formation of gaseous UO_3 to form a cubic $UThO_{3+x}$ solid solution at temperatures as low as about 1000° . During these studies an interesting fact emerged, viz., that gaseous UO_3 reacted with the ThO_2 but not with the alumina muffle tube, even though there was sufficient gaseous UO_3 present to reform and deposit crystals of U_3O_8 in the cooler parts of the muffle tube.

Known reactions² of UO_3 with other oxides show that (1) extensive solid solutions are formed with UO_3 by oxides of tri- and tetra-valent metal ions of related size and structural type, e.g., rare earth oxides with cubic Mn_2O_3 structure or the RO_2 oxides with fluorite structure, (ii) under controlled conditions, limited solid solutions are formed with oxides of heavier divalent elements. It was interesting to speculate whether the observed preferential "reactivity" of the gaseous UO_3 with ThO_2 was influenced by the substrate symmetry.

Hence this preliminary investigation was undertaken to study the influence, if any, of the symmetry of the solid substrate in determining the course of 'chemical' reactions with the gaseous UO_3 . For this purpose mainly the fourth group oxides (SiO_2 , ZrO_2 , HfO_2 , ThO_2) were chosen as these could be expected to show somewhat similar chemical behaviour and the contrasting behaviour, if observed, could be more firmly attributed to differences in their crystal structures. Stabilized zirconia was included to compare the effect of crystal structure between nearly identical oxides. CaO and CdO were chosen as representative of divalent cubic oxides of $Fm\bar{3}m$ space group, having cations of nearly the same size but different polarizabilities. Al_2O_3 was taken as a representative of the trivalent metal oxides of none cubic symmetry.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure.—Except in the case of SiO_2 , pellets of the appropriate oxide were dry pressed at 2000 Kg/cm^2 using reagent grade powder (-300 mesh B.S.S.) materials. Al_2O_3 was also used in the form of impervious fused Al_2O_3 obtained from a Morgan RR muffle tube. Fused Quartz (transparent vitreous silica) muffle pieces were used for SiO_2 . These pellets or

1. Karkhanavala & Momin, *J. Nucl. Mat.*, 1964, 11, 114.

2. Belle, "UO₃—its Properties and Nuclear Applications", USAEC, 1960.

pieces were placed on the edges of a platinum boat containing U_3O_8 , but completely out of contact with U_3O_8 . This assembly was then inserted into a horizontal tubular electric furnace electronically controlled ($\pm 5^\circ$) at the desired temperature in the range 1100–1500° and heated for 1–3 hr.

The results of some samples heated at 1400° for 3 hr. are shown in Fig. 1.

No reaction was observed with Al_2O_3 (Fig. 1.1) and SiO_2 in the entire temperature range of 1200–1800°.

FIG. 1

Pellets exposed to gaseous UO_2 at 1400° for 3 hours. (1) Al_2O_3 (2) ThO_2 (3) HfO_2 (4) ZrO_2 (5) Ca-stabilized ZrO_2 (6) Ca-stabilized ZrO_2 at 1250° for 3 hours. The dark bands show the areas which were exposed to the vapour and delineate the edges of the platinum boat.

ZrO_2 which undergoes the monoclinic to the tetragonal transformation in the range 1100–1200°, showed no reaction below about 1350°, but showed perceptible reaction at 1400° (Fig. 1.4) and above. In contrast the stabilized zirconia which remained in the cubic form throughout the range reacted even at 1100° (Figs. 1.5 and 1.6). No reaction took place with the HfO_2 which remained in the monoclinic form throughout temperature range studied.

In the case of CaO and CdO, reaction took place leading to compound formation as confirmed by x-ray analysis. The white CaO pellet, which had a very clear yellow reaction zone, is not shown as it very soon disintegrated. In case of CdO the time of exposure was shortened and temperature was kept as low as possible due to its volatility. The CdO pellet is also not shown as the reaction band, which is also blackish, can be barely distinguished visually.

DISCUSSION

The difference in the reactivity of SiO_2 and ThO_2 can be attributed to the large difference in the ionic radius of the cations and therefore in the coordination number. But while there is a large variation in the ionic size of Si^{4+} and Th^{4+} , Zr^{4+} and Hf^{4+} have nearly identical ionic radius. Hence the differences in the observed behaviour cannot be explained solely on the basis of ionic size.

That the structure is more important than ionic size is clearly brought out by a consideration of the behaviour of HfO_2 , ZrO_2 , and stabilized zirconia.

Monoclinic ZrO_2 and HfO_2 have a distorted fluorite structure. ZrO_2 undergoes a phase transformation to a tetragonal form in the range 1100 to 1190°³. This modification is almost cubic ($a=5.07 \text{ \AA}$, $c=5.16 \text{ \AA}$; $c/a=1.02 \text{ \AA}$). A cubic modification (fluorite type) exists above about 2000°. It is interesting, therefore, to note that ZrO_2 in the time allowed for the reaction showed no reaction below 1350°. But at 1400° and above there was perceptible reaction (solid solution formation) with the tetragonal form (Fig. 1.4) HfO_2 which remained monoclinic at these temperatures showed no reaction (Fig. 1.3). In contrast, stabilized zirconia showed a very noticeable reaction at 1400° (Fig. 1.5) almost as strong as with ThO_2 . The reaction was markedly observable even at 1250° (Fig. 1.6).

These observations indicate that gaseous UO_2

- (1) reacts strongly with oxides of cubic fluorite symmetry (ThO_2 , stabilized ZrO_2) forming a solid solution;
- (2) reacts with oxides of rocksalt type (CaO , CdO) forming compounds;
- (3) reacts weakly with oxides of nearly cubic symmetry (tetragonal ZrO_2);
- (4) does not react with oxides of non-cubic symmetry (Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , HfO_2 , monoclinic ZrO_2).

The present work is being extended to a systematic study of other oxides. The variations observed here are sought to be explained on structural considerations in Part II.